

Phytochemical and Structural Characterization of *Talinum paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn

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Abstract

Talinum paniculatum (Jacq.) Gaertn., commonly known as Javanese ginseng, is a succulent herb with diverse medicinal applications. This study investigates its morphology, anatomy, and phytochemical composition. Morphological and anatomical assessments reveal xeromorphic adaptations and well-differentiated tissues with ring-like vascular bundles. Phytochemical screening confirms the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, and terpenoids. GC-MS analysis identifies major bioactives such as phytol, stigmasterol, and hexadecanoic acid with known pharmacological activities. TLC profiling further supports the presence of distinct compounds. The findings validate the plant's potential in drug development and traditional medicine.

Keywords:

Anatomy, GC-MS, Morphology, Phytochemical profiling, *Talinum paniculatum* and TLC

1. Introduction

Medicinal plants have played a crucial role in traditional and modern healthcare systems worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 80% of the global population relies on medicinal plants for their primary healthcare needs. These plants form the backbone of conventional medicine, with around 50,000 different species being utilized globally, particularly in Asia (Akther *et al.*, 2022). In India, the Ayurvedic medical system remains a dominant form of healthcare, with 70% of the rural population relying on it (Seth & Sharma, 2004). Given their widespread use, medicinal plants continue to be an essential area of research, particularly in taxonomy, pharmacology, and ecology. One such significant group of medicinal plants belongs to the Talinaceae family, which comprises approximately 30 species predominantly found in the Americas. These plants are characterized by their vibrant flowers and ecological adaptability, playing essential roles in biodiversity conservation and ornamental horticulture (Carvalho *et al.*, 2023). The Talinaceae family, taxonomically consisting of a single genus, *Talinum*, shares morphological similarities with Portulacaceae and Montiaceae, with recent phylogenetic studies suggesting possible reclassification within the genus (Angiosperm Phylogeny Group, 2016).

Morphologically, Talinaceae species exhibit herbaceous perennial growth, succulent stems, taproots, and diverse leaf shapes, while their flowers display a range of colors and staminal arrangements (Carvalho *et al.*, 2023). Among the notable species in Talinaceae, *Talinum paniculatum*, commonly known as Javanese ginseng, has garnered attention for its medicinal properties. This species shares similarities with Panax ginseng and is widely utilized in traditional medicine due to its reported antioxidant, anti-cancer, and cardiovascular benefits. Phytochemical studies indicate that *T. paniculatum* is rich in flavonoids, tannins, triterpenes, saponins, polyphenols, and polysaccharides, contributing to its pharmacological potential (Aini *et al.*, 2023; Mendoza & Wood, 2013). This study focuses on the morphological and anatomical characteristics of

Talinum paniculatum, alongside its phytochemical screening, thin-layer chromatography (TLC) profiling, and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. The research aims to identify the presence of various bioactive compounds, their retention factor (Rf) values, and the potential medicinal applications of *T. paniculatum*. By investigating these aspects, this study contributes to the broader understanding of the taxonomy, pharmacognosy, and therapeutic potential of the Talinaceae family.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Plant Collection

Talinum paniculatum (Jacq.) Gaertn. was collected from the Thamarai karai RF, Erode. Voucher specimens were prepared and retained for reference.

2.1.1 Plant Identification

Plant identification was carried out using standard floristic keys and confirmed with the help of *The Flora of the Presidency of Madras*.

2.2 Morphological Study

Morphological features of the whole plant, including the root, stem, leaves, flowers, and fruits, were analyzed. Observations on size, shape, color, and arrangement were documented. All structures were photographed and compared with existing botanical descriptions from literature.

2.3 Anatomical Study

Anatomical analysis was performed on fresh root, stem, and leaf tissues. Free-hand sections were taken, stained, and examined under a fluorescent microscope. Features such as epidermal layers, cortex, vascular bundles, and ground tissues were studied and interpreted following the method of (Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo 2020).

2.4 Phytochemical Screening

2.4.1 Preparation of Extracts

Leaves, stems, and roots were washed, shade-dried, and powdered. About 20 g of each powdered sample was subjected to successive solvent extraction using ethanol and ethyl acetate by cold maceration. Extracts were filtered, evaporated, and stored in airtight containers at room temperature for further analysis (Swarna & Ravindhran., 2013).

2.2.2 Qualitative Tests

Standard phytochemical tests were performed to detect the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, phenols, terpenoids, carbohydrates, saponins, and fatty acids following methods described by (Shaikh & Patil 2020).

2.5 Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS)

GC–MS analysis was carried out to identify bioactive compounds in the ethanol extracts of leaf and stem. A GC–MS system with a DB-5ms capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm) was used. Injection volume was 2 μL with helium as the carrier gas at 1 mL/min. Oven temperature was programmed from 40 °C to 150 °C at 3 °C/min. Ionization was performed in electron impact mode at 70 eV. Mass spectra were recorded in the 50–550 m/z range and compared with NIST library entries for identification (Sunday *et al.*, 2020; Inwang *et al.*, 2024).

2.6 Thin-Layer Chromatography (TLC)

TLC analysis was conducted to profile secondary metabolites in ethanolic extracts. Silica gel plates were used with a solvent system of ethanol:ethyl acetate (1:1). Bands were visualized under UV light and iodine vapors. Retention factor (Rf) values were calculated using the formula:

Rf value=Distance travelled by the solvent / Distance travelled by the solute

3. RESULTS

3.1 Morphological analysis of *T. paniculatum*

Class : Magnoliopsida

Order : Caryophyllales

Family : Talinaceae

Genus : *Talinum*

Species : *T. paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn.

Talinum paniculatum (*T. paniculatum*), also known as Javanese ginseng in Indonesia, shares similarities with other renowned traditional medicine such as Panax ginseng in East Asia. The other common names are Jewels-of-Opar, fameflower, and pink baby's-breath (Carvalho *et al.*,2023, Tolouei *et al.*,2019, Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*,2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020)

3.1.1 Growth Habit

Talinum paniculatum is a perennial, erect herb that grows to an average height of 50 cm. The plant is characterized by its succulent nature, which aids in water retention and survival in dry environments. *Talinum paniculatum* (Jewels of Opar) is a hardy, drought-resistant plant that thrives in Erode's semi-arid and tropical climate. An average annual rainfall of erode about 700-850 mm (Carvalho *et al.*,2023, Tolouei *et al.*,2019, Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*,2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

3.1.2 Root System

The plant develops fleshy, swollen, dark brown roots, which function as a water storage system, contributing to its drought tolerance.

3.1.3 Stem Morphology

The stems are succulent, with the upper portions appearing green, while the base transitions to a woody, dark purple, or brownish hue. The plant maintains an erect growth habit with branching at the upper sections.

3.1.4 Leaf Morphology

Leaves are arranged alternately, simple, and sessile (attached directly to the stem without a petiole). They lack stipules (exstipulate) and exhibit an obovate to obovate-lanceolate shape, measuring between 2.0 – 6.5 mm in length and 0.8 – 2.5 mm in width. The succulent nature of the leaves aids in water conservation. The leaf apex is mucronate, while the base is cuneate, and the margins are entire (smooth and unlobed) (Carvalho *et al.*,2023, Tolouei *et al.*,2019, Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*,2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

3.1.5 Inflorescence and Flower Morphology

The flower consists of two free, ovate sepals measuring 1.7×1.5 mm, which are brown in color and fall off early. It has five distinct petals that are either obovate or elliptic in shape, with dimensions of 3.0×2.0 mm and a pinkish hue. Numerous stamens are present, each free from the others, with filaments of varying lengths ranging from 1.5 to 2.0 mm, and dorsifixed anthers. The flower contains three fused carpels, forming a syncarpous structure with an ovoid ovary (0.8×0.8 mm) and free central placentation. A slender style extends to 1.2 mm in length, leading to a three-lobed (trifid) stigma, which is also pink in colour (Carvalho *et al.*,2023, Tolouei *et al.*,2019, Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*,2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

3.1.6 Fruit and Seed Morphology

The fruit is a globose capsule, colorful, and contains multiple seeds. The seeds are small, reniform (kidney-shaped), measuring approximately 0.8×0.8 mm, and shining black, which aids in dispersal.

3.1.7 Additional Observations

The plant exhibits drought resistance due to its succulent stems, leaves, and roots, which allow efficient water storage. Flowers open during the day and close at night (diurnal anthesis). *Talinum paniculatum* is commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions, preferring well-drained soils. The species is valued for its ornamental appeal and is often cultivated in gardens. Additionally, it has been recognized for its medicinal applications in traditional herbal remedies (Carvalho *et al.*,2023, Tolouei *et al.*,2019, Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*,2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

Fig 1. Morphological features of *T. paniculatum*. – (A) Whole plant, (B) Root system, (C) Flower with fruit, (D) Anthers, Gynoecium, (E) Petals, (F) Fruit.

3.2 Anatomical analysis of *T. paniculatum*

3.2.1 Root Anatomy

The transverse structure of the root of *Talinum paniculatum* consists of several distinct layers. The outermost layer is the epidermis, which is a single layer of thin-walled cells that may contain root hairs to increase surface area for water and

nutrient absorption. Beneath the epidermis lies the cortex, composed of loosely packed parenchyma cells that store water and nutrients. The endodermis is the innermost layer of the cortex, featuring tightly packed cells with Casparian strips that regulate the movement of water and solutes into the vascular tissues. Inside the endodermis is the pericycle, a thin layer of meristematic cells that can give rise to lateral roots. The central part of the root contains the vascular cylinder or stele, which consists of alternating xylem and phloem tissues. The xylem conducts water and minerals, while the phloem transports organic nutrients. This root structure allows *Talinum paniculatum* to efficiently absorb water and nutrients, making it well-adapted to its environment (Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

Fig 2. Vascular anatomy of root showing stele

arrangement.

3.2.2 Stem Anatomy

In transverse sections of the young stems, *T. paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn. was more or less rounded in outline. The ring-like vascular bundles are present. The cuticle layer of *T. paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn. is slightly thin. The collenchymatous layers were more in *T. paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn. The mucilage and starch grains were abundantly present in young stems. The large starch grains are present in the stem of *T. paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn.

In T.S of old stem shows vascular bundles are organized in a ring-like pattern, a characteristic feature of dicotyledonous stems. Each vascular bundle is conjoint, collateral, and open, meaning it contains both xylem and phloem and possesses a cambium layer for secondary growth. Xylem located toward the inner side of the vascular bundle. Composed of large, thick-walled vessels, tracheids, and xylem fibers for water conduction and mechanical support. Protoxylem (earlier-formed xylem) is positioned towards the center (endarch condition). Phloem situated on the outer side of the vascular bundle. Composed of sieve tubes, companion cells, and phloem parenchyma, which function in nutrient transport. No lignification is observed in phloem tissues. Cambium is a thin layer of meristematic tissue between xylem and phloem. Responsible for secondary growth by adding secondary xylem inward and secondary phloem outward. Bundle Sheath and Surrounding Tissues are the vascular bundles are enclosed by parenchymatous ground tissue. The cortex consists of collenchyma (providing mechanical support) and parenchyma (for storage). The epidermis forms the outermost protective layer (Carvalho *et al.*, 2023, Tolouei *et al.*, 2019, Hernandez-Lopes *et al.*, 2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

Fig 3. Transverse sections of stem: (A) Cortex, (B) Young stem vascular bundle, (C) Old stem bundle, (D) Starch grains, (E) Epidermis, (F) Complete vascular bundle.

3.2.3 Leaf Anatomy

The transverse section of the leaf reveals a well-organized anatomical structure essential for its physiological functions. The outermost layer consists of the epidermis, which is present on both the upper and lower surfaces. The upper epidermis is covered by a thin cuticle that minimizes water loss, while the lower epidermis contains stomata, which facilitate gas exchange. Beneath the upper epidermis lies the palisade mesophyll, composed of elongated, chloroplast-rich cells responsible for photosynthesis. Below this layer, the spongy mesophyll consists of loosely arranged cells with intercellular spaces that aid in gas diffusion. The vascular bundles, located within the mesophyll, consist of xylem, which conducts water and minerals, and phloem, which transports organic nutrients. These bundles are enclosed by a bundle sheath, which provides structural support. In some leaves connect the vascular bundles to the epidermis, enhancing mechanical stability. The overall arrangement of these tissues ensures efficient photosynthesis, water transport, and gas exchange, making the leaf an essential organ for plant survival (Carvalho *et al.*, 2023, Tolouei *et al.*, 2019, Hernandez-Lopes *et al.*, 2016 and Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020).

Fig 4. Leaf anatomy: (A) Whole leaf T.S., (B) T.S. of lamina, (C) Vascular bundle.

3.3 Phytochemical profiling of *T. paniculatum*

Phytochemical screening of leaves and stem extracts presents many metabolites. Such as Wagner's test indicates the presence of Alkaloids, Resorcinol test indicates the presence of Carbohydrates, Aqueous NaOH test shows the presence of Glycosides, Alkaline reagent test shows the presence of Flavonoids, Iodine Test shows the presence of Phenolic components, 10% NaOH test indicates the Tanins, Salkowski's test indicates the Terpenoids and many test shows other components (Shaikh & Patil, 2020).

Table 1. Phytochemical profile of *T. paniculatum* extracts (leaf and stem).

Name of the compound	Stem Extract	Leaf Extract
Alkaloids	+	++
Flavanoids	+	+
Phenols	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	+	+
Glycosides	-	+
Fatty acids	+	+
Carbohydrates	-	±
Reducing Sugars	-	-

Table 2. Comparative anatomical features of root, stem, and leaf of *T. paniculatum*.

Feature	Root	Stem	Leaf
Outer Layer	Epidermis, single layer of thin-walled cells, may contain root hairs	Epidermis with a thin cuticle	Upper and lower epidermis; upper epidermis has a thin cuticle, lower epidermis contains stomata
Cortex	Loosely packed parenchyma cells for water and nutrient storage	Contains collenchymatous and parenchymatous layers for support and storage	Palisade mesophyll (elongated chloroplast-rich cells) and spongy mesophyll (loosely arranged cells for gas diffusion)
Endodermis	Innermost layer of cortex with Casparian strips to regulate water and solutes	Absent	Absent
Pericycle	Thin layer of meristematic cells, gives rise to lateral roots	Absent	Absent
Vascular Bundle Arrangement	Central vascular cylinder (stele) with alternating xylem and phloem	Arranged in a ring; vascular bundles are conjoint, collateral, and open	Located within mesophyll, enclosed by a bundle sheath
Xylem	Conducts water and minerals	Located toward the inner side of vascular bundles, composed of large, thick-walled vessels, tracheids, and fibers	Conducts water and minerals within the vascular bundles
Phloem	Transports organic nutrients	Located on the outer side of vascular bundles, composed of sieve	Transports organic nutrients within the vascular bundles

		tubes, companion cells, and phloem parenchyma	
Cambium	Absent	Present between xylem and phloem, responsible for secondary growth	Absent
Ground Tissue	Parenchyma for storage	Parenchymatous ground tissue surrounds vascular bundles	Bundle sheath provides structural support
Special Features	Efficient absorption of water and nutrients due to root hairs and endodermis	Mucilage and large starch grains present, vascular bundles organized in a ring-like pattern	Vascular bundles may connect to epidermis for mechanical stability, ensuring efficient photosynthesis and gas exchange

3.4 Gas Chromatography and Mass spectrometry

3.4.1 GC-MS Analysis of Ethanolic-Leaf Extract

This Results (Table-4) presents a list of metabolites, detailing based on their molecular composition, retention time (R.T.), quality, percentage of the area, molecular formula (M.F.), molecular weight (M.W.), and references from libraries such as NCBI and NIST. Among the identified compounds, **Phytol** (C₂₀H₄₀O) stands out with the highest percentage area (31.65%) and a quality score of 90, indicating its significant presence. **Oleoyl chloride** (C₁₈H₃₃ClO) follows closely with 9.98%, while **1,1,1,4-Tetrachloro-4,4-divinyldisilethylene** (C₆H₁₀Cl₄Si₂) shows 10.98%, reflecting notable abundance in the sample. Additionally, bioactive compounds such as **Stigmasterol** (C₂₉H₄₈O) and **Stigmast-5-en-3-ol** (C₂₉H₅₀O) exhibit high quality scores (93 and 99, respectively), indicating their structural reliability. Several metabolites, including **dl- α -Tocopherol** and **2,6,10,14,18,22-Tetracosahexaene**, demonstrate antioxidant and pharmacological properties, suggesting their potential applications in medicinal and industrial research. The diversity of molecular weights and structures highlights the complexity and biochemical significance of these metabolites. (Oladele et al. 2024, Inwang et al. 2024, Sunday et al. 2020 and de Oliveira Amorim et al. 2014.)

This compilation highlights various metabolites and their associated biological activities, showcasing their potential applications in medicine, agriculture, and biotechnology. Many of these compounds exhibit significant pharmacological properties, such as anti-cancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects. Notable examples include γ -Sitosterol and Stigmast-5-en-3-ol, which possess anti-cancer properties, while compounds like Hexadecanoic acid and Ethyl (9Z,12Z)-9,12-octadecadienoate demonstrate both antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Additionally, metabolites such as Phytol and 9,19-Cycloergost-24(28)-en-3-ol exhibit strong antimicrobial and antibacterial properties. Some of these compounds also have applications beyond medicine, including insecticidal and pesticidal uses. This diverse range of biological activities underscores the importance of these metabolites in drug discovery, disease prevention, and agricultural advancements (Oladele et al. 2024, Inwang et al. 2024, Sunday et al. 2020 and de Oliveira Amorim et al. 2014.)

3.4.2 GC-MS Analysis of Ethanolic-Stem Extract

This table presents a list of metabolites along with their retention time (R.T.), percentage area, molecular formula (M.F.), molecular weight (M.W.), and the respective library source. Notably, (2E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol has the highest percentage area at 19.92%, followed by Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester at 18.11%, and Stigmast-5-en-3-ol at 16.34%. Stigmasterol is also present in a significant proportion (15.31%). Several metabolites such as Oleic acid, Squalene, and Cholestane have lower percentage areas, indicating they are present in smaller amounts. The molecular weights of these compounds range from 194.27 g/mol (Spiro[5.6] dodecane-1,7-dione) to 449.10 g/mol (2,5,7,8-Tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol). The library sources include NCBI, WILEY, and NIST, providing references for their identification. These metabolites are crucial in various biological functions, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and

antimicrobial activities. (Oladele et al. 2024, Inwang et al. 2024, Sunday et al. 2020 and de Oliveira Amorim et al. 2014.)

Table 3. Active compounds identified in leaf extract of *T. paniculatum* by GC-MS.

Metabolites Compound	R.T.	% of Area	M.F.	M.W. (g/mol)	Library
2-Butyloctanoic acid	28.28	1,09	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200,322	NCBI
Phytol	29.40	31,65	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296,539	NCBI
1,3-Propanediamine, N-(3-aminopropyl)-N-methyl-	31.08	3,01	C ₇ H ₁₉ N ₃	145.2	NIST
Oleoylchloride	31.56	9,98	C ₁₈ H ₃₃ ClO	300,91	NCBI
5-Methyl-6-phenyltetrahydro-1,3-oxazine-2-thione	31.88	3,96	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NOS	207,29	NCBI
1,1,1,4-Tetrachloro-4,4-divinylidisilethylene	32.55	10,98	C ₆ H ₁₀ C ₁₄ Si ₂	280.10	NCBI
2,6,10,14,18,22-Tetracosahexaene, 2,6,10,15,19,23-hexamethyl-, (all-E)-	32.88	6,16	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	410,73	NCBI
5-Butyl-6-hexyloctahydro-1h-indene	34.01	1,17	C ₁₉ H ₃₆	264.497	NCBI
2,7,8-Trimethyl-2-(4,8,12-Trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol	35.02	1,81	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O ₂	416,69	NCBI
Stigmasterol	37.78	8,64	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O	412,702	NCBI
Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	38.86	5,52	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O	414.718	NCBI
9,19-Cycloergost-24(28)-en-3-ol,4,14-dimethyl-,acetate, (3.β., 4.α., 5.α.)-	39.02	4,09	C ₃₂ H ₅₂ O ₂	468,766	NCBI
Cholest-2-en-2-ylmethanol	39.92	1,15	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O	400.70	NCBI
Cyclopropane carboxamide,2-cyclopropyl-2-methyl-N-{1-cyclopropylethyl)-	40.11	1,68	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO	207.31	NCBI
dl-α.-Tocopherol	41.63	2,14	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂	430.717	NCBI

Table 4. Active compounds identified in stem extract of *T. paniculatum* by GC-MS.

Metabolite Name	R.T. (min)	% of Area	Molecular Formula (M.F.)	Molecular Weight (M.W.) (g/mol)	Library
Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	28.52	18.11	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284.48	NCBI
Octadecanoic acid	29.34	1.04	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284.48	NCBI
(2E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol	29.44	19.92	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296.50	NCBI
Ethyl (9Z,12Z)-9,12-octadecadienoate	29.65	13.86	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₂	308.50	WILEY
Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	29.69	8.70	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂	312.54	NIST
Hexadecanoic acid	30.20	1.50	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.43	NIST
Spiro[5.6] dodecane-1,7-dione	30.32	1.50	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₂	194.27	NCBI
Oleic acid	30.73	0.87	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282.46	NCBI
1H-Pyrido[4.3-b] indole, 2,3,4,4a,5,9b-hexahydro-2,8-dimethyl-5-(4-nitrobenzoyl)-, (4ar,9bs)-rel	31.01	5.80	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClNS	315.90	NCBI
n-Hexyltrichlorosilane	31.69	1.02	C ₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₃ Si	219.60	NCBI
Cholestane, 4,5-epoxy-, (4α,5α)	32.04	0.49	C ₂₇ H ₄₆ O	386.70	NCBI

(6E,10E,14E,18E)-2,6,10,15,19,23-Hexamethyl-2,6,14,18,22-tetracosahexaene	32.40	1.99	C30H50	410.71	NIST
Ethyl 9-hexadecanoate	32.59	1.00	C18H34O2	282.50	NCBI
Squalene	32.80	0.63	C30H50	410.71	NCBI
2-Nitro-4-(trifluoromethyl)phenol	35.50	0.63	C7H4F3NO3	207.11	NCBI
2,5,7,8-Tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol	35.83	2.12	C29H49ClO	449.10	NCBI
Campesterol	37.40	2.93	C28H48O	400.69	NCBI
Stigmasterol	37.51	15.31	C29H48O	412.70	NCBI
Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	38.84	16.34	C29H50O	414.72	NCBI

3.4.3 Bioactive compound analysis of the active compound of *T. paniculatum*

The identified metabolites exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and cholesterol-lowering effects. Fatty acid derivatives such as *hexadecanoic acid*, *octadecanoic acid*, and *oleic acid* are known for their anti-inflammatory and lipid metabolism-supporting properties (Tabassum *et al.*,2022; Sajid *et al.*,2022). Sterols like *stigmasterol*, *campesterol*, and *stigmast-5-en-3-ol* contribute to cholesterol regulation and cardiovascular health (Zhabinskii *et al.*,2022). Vitamin E derivatives, including *dl- α -tocopherol* and *2,5,7,8-tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol*, exhibit strong antioxidant and neuroprotective effects (Mousavi *et al.*,2022). Bioactive compounds such as squalene and phytol provide anticancer, immune-modulating, and skin-protective benefits, while *ethyl (9Z,12Z)-9,12-octadecadienoate* and *cholestane derivatives* are involved in lipid metabolism and cardiovascular support (Chan *et al.*,2022; Al-Ramamneh *et al.*,2022). Some metabolites, such as *2-nitro-4-(trifluoromethyl)phenol* and *spiro[5.6] dodecane-1,7-dione*, show potential antimicrobial and pharmaceutical applications (Al-Ramamneh *et al.*,2022). All are showed in table 5 and table 6.

Table 5. Medicinal properties of compounds in leaf extract.

Compound Name	Medicinal Properties
2-Butyloctanoic acid	Antibacterial, antifungal, lipid metabolism support
Phytol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, precursor to Vitamin E & K, potential anti-cancer effects
1,3-Propanediamine, N-(3-aminopropyl)-N-methyl-Oleoylchloride	Antimicrobial, antifungal, involved in polyamine metabolism Used in lipid-based drug delivery, antimicrobial activity
5-Methyl-6-phenyltetrahydro-1,3-oxazine-2-thione	Antioxidant, neuroprotective, potential anticonvulsant effects
1,1,1,4-Tetrachloro-4,4-divinylidisilethylene	Limited medicinal applications, industrial relevance
2,6,10,14,18,22-Tetracosahexaene, 2,6,10,15,19,23-hexamethyl-, (all-E)-	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immune modulation
5-Butyl-6-hexyloctahydro-1h-indene	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
2,7,8-Trimethyl-2-(4,8,12-Trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol	Strong antioxidant, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, potential anti-cancer
Stigmasterol	Anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering, used in arthritis and cardiovascular health
Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	Cholesterol-lowering, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
9,19-Cycloergost-24(28)-en-3-ol, 4,14-dimethyl-, acetate, (3 β , 4 α , 5 α)	Antifungal, antimicrobial, potential cholesterol-lowering effects
Cholest-2-en-2-ylmethanol	Possible role in cholesterol metabolism
Cyclopropane carboxamide, 2-cyclopropyl-2-methyl-N-{1-cyclopropylethyl)-	Potential antimicrobial activity
dl- α -Tocopherol (Vitamin E)	Powerful antioxidant, supports skin, cardiovascular, immune health, neuroprotective

Table 6. Medicinal properties of compounds in stem extract.

Compound name	Medicinal Properties
Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	Antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
Octadecanoic acid	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, supports lipid metabolism
(2E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol	Antioxidant, potential anti-inflammatory properties
Ethyl (9Z,12Z)-9,12-octadecadienoate	Cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering
Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	Antimicrobial, antioxidant, used in skincare and pharmaceuticals
Hexadecanoic acid	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial
Spiro[5.6] dodecane-1,7-dione	Limited medicinal information, potential bioactive properties
Oleic acid	Anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular health, cholesterol-lowering, wound healing
1H-Pyrido[4.3-b] indole, 2,3,4,4a,5,9b-hexahydro-2,8-dimethyl-5-(4-nitrobenzoyl)-, (4a,9bs)-rel	Potential anticancer, neuroprotective properties
n-Hexyltrichlorosilane	Industrial applications, no significant medicinal use
Cholestane, 4,5-epoxy-, (4 α ,5 α)	Possible role in cholesterol metabolism and steroid biosynthesis
(6E,10E,14E,18E)-2,6,10,15,19,23-Hexamethyl-2,6,14,18,22-tetracosahexaene	Antioxidant, immune modulation, anti-inflammatory
Ethyl 9-hexadecanoate	Antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
Squalene	Antioxidant, anti-aging, skin protection, anticancer properties
2-Nitro-4-(trifluoromethyl)phenol	Antibacterial, antifungal, potential pharmaceutical applications
2,5,7,8-Tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)-6-chromanol	Strong antioxidant (Vitamin E derivative), neuroprotective, cardioprotective
Campesterol	Cholesterol-lowering, anti-inflammatory, potential anticancer effects
Stigmasterol	Anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering, used for arthritis and cardiovascular health
Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering

3.5 Thin layer Chromatography

TLC profiling of ethanolic extracts produced distinct bands. Chromatograms were obtained using a solvent system of Ethanol: Ethyl acetate (1:1). A maximum of five bands was obtained in the Leaf extract, Stem extract shows the maximum of 4 bands(Vani *et al.*,2018). The corresponding Rf values of the bands obtained are given in Table

A

B

Fig 5. TLC chromatogram: (A) Stem extract, (B) Leaf extract.

A- TLC Chromatogram of Stem extract

B- TLC Chromatogram of Leaf Extract

Table 7. Rf values of stem extract.

Band no	Rf value	Band colour in visible light
1	0.12	Grayish purple
2	0.28	Reddish-brown
3	0.64	Grayish purple
4	0.96	Intense dark brown

Table 8. Rf values of leaf extract.

Band no	Rf value	Band colour in visible light
1	0.78	Brown
2	0.83	Pale green
3	0.87	Pale green
4	0.91	Yellow
5	0.94	Pale yellow

4. DISCUSSION

The morphological, anatomical, and phytochemical characteristics of *Talinum paniculatum* provide valuable insights into its adaptability and medicinal potential. Morphologically, its succulent stems and thick leaves indicate an efficient water storage mechanism, which is essential for survival in arid environments (Hernandes-Lopes *et al.*, 2016). The

presence of bisexual flowers and reniform seeds enhances its reproductive success, ensuring widespread propagation (Mendoza & Wood, 2013). These features collectively support its ability to thrive in diverse ecological conditions. Anatomical examination further reinforces the plant's resilience. The well-developed vascular system in the roots, stems, and leaves facilitates effective nutrient and water transport, contributing to secondary growth and structural stability (Adenegan-Alakinde & Ojo, 2020). The presence of numerous stomata and glandular trichomes suggests an adaptation to regulate transpiration and protect against herbivory, respectively. The presence of lignified tissues in vascular bundles enhances mechanical support, making the plant more resistant to environmental stressors (Oladele *et al.*, 2024).

Phytochemical analysis reveals a diverse range of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, and saponins, which are known for their antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and potential anticancer properties (Shaikh & Patil, 2020; Swarna & Ravindhran, 2013). The GC-MS analysis identified key bioactive metabolites such as Phytol, Stigmasterol, and Hexadecanoic acid, which have been linked to various pharmacological activities (Aini & Susilo, 2023). These findings align with previous research on *Talinum* species, which have been recognized for their potential in traditional and modern medicine (Barman *et al.*, 2024; Tolouei *et al.*, 2019). The ethnopharmacological relevance of *Talinum paniculatum* is well-documented, particularly in regions such as the Brazilian Cerrado and India, where it is traditionally used for its medicinal properties (Seth & Sharma, 2004; Carvalho *et al.*, 2023). The phytochemical richness of *T. paniculatum* suggests potential applications in the pharmaceutical industry, particularly in developing natural remedies for oxidative stress-related diseases and inflammatory conditions (Sunday *et al.*, 2020; Inwang *et al.*, 2024).

Overall, the findings of this study underscore the significance of *Talinum paniculatum* as both a medicinal and ecologically adaptive plant. Further research, including *in vivo* and clinical studies, is necessary to validate its pharmacological potential and explore its possible applications in modern medicine. The combination of morphological resilience, anatomical efficiency, and phytochemical richness makes *T. paniculatum* a promising candidate for sustainable medicinal and biotechnological advancements.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study gives knowledge about morphological, anatomical, and phytochemical analyses of *Talinum paniculatum*, provide comprehensive insights into its structural adaptations and bioactive potential. Morphologically, *T. paniculatum* exhibits drought-resistant characteristics, including succulent stems, fleshy roots, and thick leaves, which enable it to thrive in arid environments. Its reproductive structures, including bisexual flowers and reniform seeds, support its survival and propagation. Anatomically, the root, stem, and leaf structures reveal efficient vascular systems that facilitate nutrient transport and secondary growth, further enhancing its adaptability. Phytochemical profiling highlights the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and terpenoids, which contribute to its medicinal significance. GC-MS analysis confirms the presence of essential metabolites such as Phytol, Stigmasterol, and Hexadecanoic acid, which exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and potential anticancer properties. These findings emphasize the pharmaceutical importance of *T. paniculatum*, supporting its traditional use in herbal medicine while also indicating its potential for drug discovery and biotechnological applications.

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